

Equilibrium constants for the pH-dependent axial ligation of alkyl(aquo)cobaloximes by pyridine and substituted pyridines

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Manuscript received 23 September 2002, accepted 13 February 2003

Equilibria for the reaction of alkyl(aquo)cobaloximes (R = CH₃, C₂H₅) with pyridine and substituted pyridines (4-methylpyridine, 4-ethylpyridine, 4-aminopyridine, 2-ethylpyridine and 2-aminopyridine) were studied as a function of pH at 25°, 1.0 M ionic strength (KCl) by spectrophotometric technique. Affinity of binding was interpreted based on the basicity of incoming ligand, steric effect and nature of alkyl group *trans* to H₂O in cobaloxime. 2-Aminopyridine and 2-ethylpyridine binds to alkylcobaloxime very weakly due to the steric hindrance caused by the substituent at C₂ of pyridine.

Since the discovery of Co–C bond in adenosylcobalamin¹, there has been considerable interest in the chemistry of the cleavage of this bond, which is extremely rare in nature. A considerable amount of effort has been put in trying to understand, what causes the 10¹² enhancement of the Co–C bond cleavage rate of AdoCbl in presence of enzyme^{2,3}. Cobaloximes have been crucial in providing a foundation for understanding the chemistry of more complex molecule coenzyme B₁₂. In vit-B₁₂ coenzyme mediated reactions, the widely accepted key step is homolytic cleavage of Co–C bond^{4–6}.

The study of simple models of the vit-B₁₂ coenzyme such as the cobaloximes, RCo(DH)₂L, where L = neutral ligand and R = alkyl group, has furnished a significant amount of data^{7,8}, that have provided a foundation for understanding the behavior of cobalamins⁹. These cobaloximes have been the subject of extensive kinetic and mechanistic studies^{10,11}. Equilibria and kinetics of axial ligation of methyl(aquo)-cobaloxime with a series of five primary amines was studied¹². Synthesis, thermodynamics and kinetic behavior of [pyM(DH)₂R] with M = Co (cobaloxime), Rh (Rhodoximes), R = a bulky alkyl group, was studied by Geremia *et al.*¹³. Lu *et al.*¹⁴ studied the complex formation constants for the reaction of [Co(Me₆trien)H₂O]²⁺ with different pyridine and imidazole based nucleophiles and kinetics of these reactions were studied as a function of entering ligand concentration, temperature and pressure. Recently, equilibria and kinetics of axial ligation of alkyl(aquo)-cobaloximes with imidazole and substituted imidazoles have been studied^{15–18}. Compared to cobalamins and other model systems, cobaloximes have stronger Co–C bonds¹⁹ and shorter Co–L bonds²⁰ (L = pyridines and substituted py-

ridines). Thermodynamics and kinetic studies on the reaction between the vitamin B₁₂ derivative B-(*N*-methylimidazolyl)cobalamin and *N*-methylimidazole and ligand displacement at the α -axial site of cobalamins was reported by Andrew *et al.*²¹. Kinetics and reaction mechanisms of complexes with Co–C sigma bonds of the type [(NH₃)₅-Co-R]²⁺ in aqueous solutions, a pulse radiolysis study was done by Shaham *et al.*²². Alzoubi *et al.*²³ studied the ligand substitution reactions of *trans*-[Co(en)₂(Me)H₂O]²⁺ with CN⁻, SCN⁻ and N₃⁻.

Many model complexes have shown that the ligand in the *trans*-position to the Co–C bond can effect the kinetics and thermodynamical stability. In view of this our present study deals with the substitution reactions of water with a series of pyridines and substituted pyridines with RCo(DH)₂OH₂ (where R = CH₃, C₂H₅).

Results and discussion

Determination of dissociation constants of the ligands :

Values for the pK_a of the conjugated acid of ligands are obtained by potentiometric titrations at 25 ± 0.01°.

Determination of equilibrium constants :

Apparent equilibrium constants (*K*_{app}) values, see eq. (1) for the axial ligation of alkyl(aquo)cobaloximes, were determined by spectrophotometric measurements. Solutions containing RCo(DH)₂(OH)₂ (R = CH₃, C₂H₅) an appropriate buffer (0.2 M) to maintain pH, KCl to maintain ionic strength (1.0 M) and varying concentrations of the ligand are taken in a 3 ml cuvette and allowed to equilibrate in a thermostated cell compartment holder at 25 ± 0.1° for 15 min prior to addition of cobaloxime.

$$K_{app} = \frac{[RCo(DH)_2L]}{[RCo(DH)_2H_2O][L]_{free}} \quad (1)$$

Final absorbance reading taken after equilibrium is established as indicated by the time-independence of the readings. For such experimental setups, at a given pH eq. (2) is applied for the calculation of K_{app} from the experimental data :

$$\Delta A = \Delta A_{max} [L]_f / (1/K_{app} + [L]_f) \quad (2)$$

where ΔA is the difference in absorbance between solutions containing cobaloximes, added ligand (L) and solutions containing only cobaloxime at the same concentration. ΔA_{max} is the maximum absorbance change thus obtained at high $[L]$, and $[L]_f$ the unbound ligand concentration. The data are analyzed by a least-squares fit to the rearranged form of eq. (2) to give,

$$\Delta A = \Delta A_{max} \{1/K_{app} (\Delta A/[L]_f)\} \quad (3)$$

$$[L]_f = [L]_T - (C_T \Delta A / \Delta A_{max}) \quad (4)$$

$[L]_f$ is calculated from eq. (4) using the measured values of ΔA and ΔA_{max} ; $[L]_T$ is the total concentration of added ligand and C_T the total concentration of cobaloxime. Values of K_{app} are obtained from the least-squares fit of eq. (3), i.e., from the plot of ΔA vs $\Delta A/[L]_f$ and the slope is $-1/K_{app}$.

Table 1. Formation constants $\log K_{app}$ and K_{eq} for the axial ligation of $CH_3Co(DH)_2OH_2$ by L at 25°

pH	4-Amino pyridine	4-Ethyl pyridine	4-Methyl pyridine	Pyridine	2-Amino pyridine	2-Ethyl pyridine
4.0	-	-	-	1.580	-	-
4.5	-	-	-	2.053	-	-
5.0	-	-	1.778	2.476	-	0.459
5.5	-	2.182	2.257	2.797	0.227	0.863
6.0	-	2.654	2.697	2.981	0.686	1.152
6.5	-	3.076	3.047	3.061	1.077	1.307
7.0	-	3.395	3.264	3.089	1.347	1.369
7.5	-	3.576	3.363	3.099	1.485	1.391
8.0	2.903	3.654	3.400	-	1.540	1.398
8.5	3.368	3.682	3.412	-	1.558	-
9.0	3.774	3.691	-	-	1.564	-
9.5	4.066	-	-	-	-	-
10.0	4.223	-	-	-	-	-
10.5	4.287	-	-	-	-	-
11.0	4.309	-	-	-	-	-
K_{eq}	20911.00	4968.00	2621.00	1270.00	37.00	25.00

The values for the equilibrium constants for axial ligation with respect to the unprotonated ligand are calculated from the relation, $K_{eq} = K_{app}/\alpha_L$, where α_L is calculated

from eq. (5),

$$\alpha_L = K_a / (K_a + H^+) \quad (5)$$

The values of equilibrium constant K_{app} for the reaction of various substituted pyridines with $RCo(DH)_2OH_2$, where R = CH_3 and C_2H_5 are given in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively. Plots of K_{app} vs pH for the reactions of

Table 2. Formation constants $\log K_{app}$ and K_{eq} for the axial ligation of $C_2H_5Co(DH)_2OH_2$ by L at 25°

pH	4-Amino pyridine	4-Ethyl pyridine	4-Methyl pyridine	Pyridine	2-Amino pyridine	2-Ethyl pyridine
4.0	-	-	-	1.501	-	-
4.5	-	-	-	1.974	-	-
5.0	-	-	1.585	2.398	-	0.139
5.5	-	2.005	2.064	2.718	-	0.543
6.0	-	2.478	2.503	2.903	0.419	0.832
6.5	-	2.899	2.854	2.982	0.811	0.986
7.0	-	3.218	3.071	3.011	1.080	1.049
7.5	-	3.399	3.170	3.020	1.218	1.071
8.0	2.753	3.477	3.207	-	1.273	1.079
8.5	3.219	3.505	3.219	-	1.292	-
9.0	3.625	3.515	-	-	1.298	-
9.5	3.917	-	-	-	-	-
10.0	4.073	-	-	-	-	-
10.5	4.137	-	-	-	-	-
11.0	4.160	-	-	-	-	-
K_{eq}	14822.00	3305.00	1680.00	1059.00	20.00	12.00

Fig. 1. Dependence of $\log K_{app}$ on pH for the formation of $CH_3Co(DH)_2L$ at 25°.

$CH_3Co(DH)_2OH_2$ with various pyridines (Fig. 1) reveal that as the pH increases the K_{app} increases and the affinity for the ligands are in the order : 2-ethylpyridine < 2-aminopyridine < pyridine < 4-methylpyridine < 4-

ethylpyridine < 4-aminopyridine. Though 2-ethylpyridine and 2-aminopyridine are more basic than pyridine they form less stable complexes than pyridine and 4-substituted-pyridines due to the steric hindrance of the substituents (C_2H_5 and NH_2) at C_2 of pyridine. Similar trends were observed in the study of 2-substituted-imidazoles to $RCO(DH)_2OH_2$ ^{20,21}, $[CNCO(DH)_2L]$ ²⁴ and in the binding of P (*n*-but)₃ to cobaloximes. Though P in P(*n*-but)₃ is soft²⁵ and more basic than imidazole, it binds weakly; this indicates that steric hindrance plays a dominant role.

The stability order with respect to R is $CH_3 > C_2H_5$, as the electron-donating ability of R increases Co^{III} becomes weaker Lewis acid and hence binding constants decreases,

Fig. 2. Dependence of $\log K_{app}$ on trans alkyl group in $RCo(DH)_2OH_2$ ($R = CH_3, C_2H_5$), for the formation of $RCo(DH)_2(Py)$ at 25° .

Fig. 3. Binding of $C_2H_5Co(DH)_2OH_2$ with various concentrations of pyridine at pH 6.5 at 25° .

this is shown in Fig. 2. UV-visible scans show the binding of pyridine to $C_2H_5Co(DH)_2OH_2$ as a function of concentration of pyridines (Fig. 3).

The binding constants are measured in the pH range 4–11, depending upon pK_a of the ligand. If we compare the pH-dependent binding plots of pyridines, the K_{app} increases with increase in pH and after certain pH they become pH-independent. In all the cases, there is not much significant increase in K_{app} values at the pH above pK_a of the ligand and hence the binding constants are pH-independent. Below the pK_a of the ligands, pyridine nitrogen is protonated and not much free base is available for binding to Co^{III} . As the pH increases to the pH above pK_a of the ligand pyridine free base is available completely, hence there is no change in K_{app} values above the pK_a of the ligand. Fig. 1 shows the pH dependent and independent binding of pyridines to $C_2H_5Co(DH)_2OH_2$. A soft or class b character has been assigned to cobaloxime and is consistent with the observed greater ligand affinity of pyridine and 4-substituted-pyridines than the hard glycine or glycine ester^{18, 20, 21}. Similar results were obtained in our earlier studies where imidazole and histamine form more stronger complexes than glycine²¹. The order of stability is attributed to the ability of pyridine or C_4 substituted pyridines or imidazoles to accept electrons into higher energy unfilled π^* antibonding orbital through $d\pi$ to $p\pi$ back-bonding ($Co^{III} \rightarrow N$ of pyridine). Hence imidazole and pyridines form stable complexes than glycine or glycine ester, whereas primary amine glycine or glycine ester can not accept through back-bonding.

Experimental

Pyridine, 2-aminopyridine, 2-ethylpyridine, 4 ethylpyridine, 4-methylpyridine, 4-aminopyridine (all S. D. Fine chemicals), KCl, HPLC methanol (Fluka), acetic acid, sodium acetate (E. Merck), dipotassium hydrogen phosphate, potassium dihydrogen phosphate, potassium phosphate, tris(hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (Tris), potassium hydroxide (Across) were used. Double-distilled water was used throughout.

Alkyl(aquo)cobaloximes were prepared by the reported procedure²⁶. All manipulations were performed under minimal illuminations due to photolability of the carbon-cobalt bond^{9,27}. These alkyl(aquo)cobaloximes are photolabile, particularly in solution, soluble in alcohols and DMSO, less so in chloroform or water and virtually insoluble in ether and hydrocarbon solvents.

pH values were determined with a Digisun pH meter equipped with a combined glass electrode. The electrode was standardized at two pH values (4.0 and 9.2) with stan-

ard buffer solutions. UV-visible spectra were recorded on a Hitachi U-3410 spectrophotometer.

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